

ECONOMIC SIGNIFICANCE OF STOCK MARKET

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One of the important segments of the market economy is the stock market, which serves to place temporarily idle money in securities and ensure its target location through redistribution. Such goals can be achieved only when all types of securities, both traditional and non-traditional segments of the stock market, are effective. At the same time, transactions including all operations such as placement of securities and trading with them are mainly carried out by commercial banks. This, first of all, ensures the increase of their authorized capital, and secondly, free capital abroad is mobilized with the help of commercial activities in the markets.

At the moment, stock markets and their efficient operation, their participants, and types of highly liquid securities with international status in circulation are important. The development of stock markets is directly related to the level of infrastructural development of the state, first of all, if it leads to high-speed development by ensuring the integration of the national stock market into international stock markets, and secondly, by bringing the high liquidity and financial stability of commercial banks to international standards. will come.

Another characteristic feature of stock markets is their dependence on the level of risk. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze the factors affecting the effective development of the infrastructure of the stock market and to study its specific features.

Despite the fact that the stock market of Uzbekistan is young, its history contains pages related to specific transactions on options and futures. Some option contracts were concluded in 1992 in the stock department of the "Tashkent" stock exchange. The Regulation on the option of the state property committee to sell the share of state property, as well as shares intended for free sale and sale to partners, was registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic on October 24, 1994 with number 110, according to which the privatized sale of shares (future shares) of authorized funds of enterprises was carried out.

In accordance with the regulations, over-the-counter auctions of option contracts were held, the initial prices of which were about 40% of the nominal

value of the share of the company's charter fund. The person who won the auction has the right to purchase a share of the authorized fund of the enterprise, but in the form of securities, at a fixed (usually nominal) price agreed upon in the contract by the issuer, or to withdraw from the transaction. In 1995, the Tashkent Regional Office of the State Property Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the "Tashkent" Republican Stock Exchange concluded a futures contract for the sale of state property of the Tashkent Regional State Property Office, as well as shares intended for free sale. charter was approved. The system of selling state property, as well as shares intended for free sale and sale to partners based on the futures contract, was aimed at accelerating the process of privatization, activating the stock market, and creating conditions for the formation of market prices of securities based on the sale option. In accordance with the regulation, the state property of the enterprises being privatized, as well as the shares intended for free sale and sale to partners, the futures contract (futures contract of the state property department of Tashkent region) is a bilateral contract, which guarantees the share of state property (strictly iy) purchase at a certain price during a certain period of time or at a certain future date ensured this obligation. In Uzbekistan, transactions with futures can be carried out only on stock exchanges.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Securities and Stock Exchanges" adopted on September 2, 1993, "Securities are evidence of ownership or debt relations between the person who issued them and their owner." are monetary documents that provide for the payment of dividends or income in the form of interest, as well as the possibility of transferring the rights arising from these documents to another person"

In January 1992, the Fund Department of the "Tashkent" Exchange was the first in the republic to conduct regular trading with securities. In the same year 1992, the turnover of the Fund Department of the "Tashkent" stock exchange in transactions with securities amounted to 26 million rubles, which was comparable to the same performance of the Russian stock exchanges. In its activities, the stock exchange complies with the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the charter of the stock exchange, and the business rules for carrying out work related to securities. is registered in accordance with and receives a license from the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan to carry out stock exchange activities. An organization that has not received a license to conduct stock exchange activity has no right to conduct such activity. Fund departments can be established as independent structural units and non-

independent structural units in commodity and stock exchanges and currency exchanges. Fund departments must comply with all requirements for stock exchanges in their activities. The founders of the stock exchange can be legal entities and individuals who have a permit (license) granting the right to carry out securities trading. Legal entities and individuals, including foreign legal entities and individuals, who have purchased a brokerage position at the stock exchange, may become members of the stock exchange (commodity fund or currency exchange fund department). The management bodies of the stock exchange, their officials and specialists do not have the right to be members of the stock exchange. (According to Article 2 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 7 of 22.09.2005, the words were deleted in the text) Members of the Stock Exchange have such permits to carry out securities trading and have the status of an investment institution. it will be put up for sale only in case. An individual who has purchased a brokerage seat can be put on sale only after registering it with the local authorities and having an account balance in the bank. The rules of stock exchange operations are approved by the top management body of the stock exchange.

Currently, the "Tashkent" Republican Stock Exchange is considered the main trading area of the country's securities market, where various securities are traded.

The highest indicator of the volume of transactions corresponded to the middle of February, this indicator exceeded 584.34 billion soums in one trading

day; the minimum indicator was recorded in the middle of March - the volume of transactions on March 16 was 70.80 million soums. The largest number of transactions was recorded on February 17, when 2,047 transactions were recorded in one trading day. The lowest indicator was made on February 16 and amounted to 472 transactions. In the first quarter of 2023, the average number of daily transactions on all trading platforms of RFB "Tashkent" was 774 units, and the average daily volume of transactions was 27.8 billion soums.

The experience of developed countries shows that an efficient stock market is one of the factors that positively affects economic growth. A developed stock market allows enterprises to adequately assess and diversify risks in financing projects requiring large investments, and to attract funds effectively. In addition, the stock market can serve as an indicator of economic trends, which allows stakeholders (including the government) to develop and effectively implement their own strategies.

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